

GREAT BRITAIN SCIENTIFIC AND ECONOMY JOURNAL

NATIONAL ECONOMY

ISSUE 1, (3)

JANUARY ISSUE, 1(3)

England is the most economically developed piece of Great Britain. The main centers of the country's traditional industries: mining metallurgy, metalworking, chemical, textile, food industries are located here. Mechanical engineering (automotive, aviation, machine building, Instrumentation), Electrical and radio engineering, and the nuclear industry are also well developed. In England, the largest industrial centers of the country are located: London, Birmingham, Liverpool and others. A small 70% of the total crop of Great Britain falls on England. It is also the main site of dairy cattle breeding, vegetable growing and horticulture. In England, the transport network is thick, more than 80% of the country's cargo turnover passes through its ports (London, Liverpool, Southampton, etc.). See also Great Britain.[1]

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ADDITIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES	3
Mamatkulova Nadira Makhkamovna	
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ IGCT ТИРИСТОРА	5
Халмирзаева Шавкатбек Курбанович	
EXPLORING WAYS TO USE THE THEORY OF MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING	10
Qosimova Zarguloy Abinjon qizi	
TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHRAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING AHAMIYATI	15
Turdaliyeva Og'iloy	
IMPROVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN CONSTRUCTION	17
Orazimbet Janabaev; Guljamal Uderbaeva	
BIRINCHI SINIF O'QUVCHILARIGA GEOMETRIK SHAKLLARNI O'RGATISH USULLARI	19
Asliddinova Durdona	

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ADDITIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

Abstract:

The technological process does not stand still, every day there is an improvement in digital technologies, which allows the use of innovations in various areas of human life. Additive technologies are among the most advanced and in demand all over the world. The article discusses the effectiveness of additive technologies in industrial enterprises. The advantages of additive technologies and their difference from traditional production are described.

Key words:

additive technologies, 3D printer, digital technologies, traditional production, non-waste production, environmental safety, environmental protection.

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Additive manufacturing is a modern and efficient method of creating 3D and 3D objects using a 3D printer. Global manufacturers of modern technologies, such as General Electrics and Boeing, have long begun to use additive manufacturing as an integral part of their business processes. The additive method has a number of advantages over traditional production: it is faster, cheaper, much more versatile and more cost-effective. Became possible to build a house in a few days or make engine parts in a few hours can with additive technologies.

Depending on the final result, there are several areas of application of additive technologies:

- Making parts (Rapid Patterns) that will be used as templates for the final product. Often used in jewelry.
- Making molds (Rapid Tooling) using additive methods. Then they can be used for molding and casting products.
- Direct digital manufacturing (Direct Digital Manufacturing, DDM) - manufacturing in additive ways of the final product.

Dynamically developing at a rapid pace, additive 3D printing technologies are used in progressive industries. There are several innovative types of additive technologies:

1. FDM (Fused deposition modeling) - the product is formed in layers from a melted plastic thread.
2. CJP (ColorJet printing) is the only full-color 3d printing in the world with the principle of gluing a powder consisting of gypsum.
3. SLS (Selective Laser Sintering) is a laser sintering technology that produces extremely strong objects of any size.
4. MJM (MultiJet Modeling) multi-jet 3d modeling using photopolymers and wax.
5. SLA (Laser Stereolithography) - layer-by-layer hardening of a liquid polymer occurs with the help of a laser.

In industry, the production of 3D products goes through several general stages (they may vary depending on methods and materials):

- 3D modeling or product sketching (Computer Aided Design or CAD).
- Creation of a reduced copy of the product from a cheaper material, for example, inexpensive plastic instead of metal.
- Printing the product itself after the copy has passed the test. The printer follows the sketch and adds layers of liquid, powder, or sheet material and produces the part, sometimes in just a few hours.

Advantages of additive technologies and their difference from traditional production:

- Speed of production. With traditional methods, a complex part can be produced within months, but with 3D printing, it can be done in a few hours. After manufacturing, additional machining is often not needed.
- Waste-free production. In traditional manufacturing, there is a high risk of sending an incorrectly manufactured part to waste. When using additive methods, if the metal part does not work out, it can be turned into powder again and the same product is printed from it again.
- Lack of seams and welded joints. Unlike traditional production, with the help of additive technologies it is possible to obtain products with unique properties, without seams and joints. Such objects cannot be made by welding and stamping.

In recent years, houses built using the construction 3D printing method have appeared. Special building printers create either small cottages or building elements, which are then assembled on site into a whole building.

Technology makes it possible to build houses very quickly and cheaply. Building areas are still small, but this is temporary.

Additive manufacturing of buildings and various structures significantly reduces construction time. Construction 3D printing is trending all over the world. Experiments carried out on laser 3d printers for ordinary people look on the verge of fantastic. Additive 3D technologies - positive aspects in construction:

- saving time and financial costs (speed of erection in a matter of days, lower costs for logistics, consumables, hiring a large number of personnel);
- implementation of any design solutions and complex geometric shapes (medieval castles, houses in the form of asteroids and galaxies);
- Possibility to build earthquake-resistant houses in areas prone to earthquakes and hurricanes.

The use of 3D printing, among other things, accelerates the digitalization of production processes, because additive manufacturing is a purely digital technology. It does not require technological equipment, and therefore, allows you to reduce or even eliminate the cost of switching production between different types of equipment and several sections of the plant. This is a radical departure from the traditional labour-intensive production methods used in the last 150 years in the industrial sector, when achieving the target level of costs, especially in the price-sensitive consumer goods market, required the aggregation of large volumes of production on one site.

In reality, the most revolutionary aspect of additive manufacturing has little to do with 3D printers directly. The key point is that additive technologies allow you to translate a digital form into a physical product. A 3D printing file is a finished product, while a project (prototype) is a compromise between the final, desired product and the capabilities of a traditional manufacturing process. Thus, we can say that 3D printing is a significant step towards a radical digital transformation of production.

Moreover, the digitalization of production affects not only the stages of manufacturing products, but also all related processes, including supply chains and ways of storing parts. Warehouses overloaded with components that can become obsolete and unclaimed are a thing of the past. Additive manufacturing converts piles of boxes that eat up physical space into digital files that can be stored in the cloud and accessed whenever needed. In addition to digital storage, 3D printing provides another important opportunity - expanding the network of localization of production sites, which allows companies to consider the introduction of additive technologies in the context of strategic business planning.

The expansion of the network of localization of production sites, in fact, is the decentralization of production facilities, in other words, the organization of several small production facilities near potential consumers instead of one large plant, where all the equipment and all the company's resources are concentrated.

So, Jabil uses the capabilities of additive technologies to organize a network of factories, which allows you to quickly move production loads from one geographic market to another, while the costs of changing technological processes and "tuning" the product to a specific consumer are minimal. This would not have been possible without digital 3D printing technology. Thus, additive manufacturing allows you to effectively combine real-life component deliveries with digital ones (part files), which provides ample opportunities for product management at all stages of its life cycle, from concept to end-of-life. Production processes can be quickly moved to any site that has the right digital equipment, for this you just need to download and send the required file. Production is no longer rigidly tied to one plant and established supply chains. This means that in the event of a global problem like the current pandemic, the manufacturer has more opportunities to respond quickly and flexibly: reorganize supply chains and readjust production processes at other points in the production network. This flexibility gives the industry a "margin of safety" in difficult economic conditions, which, in turn, increases the reliability of the global market as a whole.

Two more important aspects of additive manufacturing are environmental safety and environmental protection. One of the indisputable advantages of 3D printing is the reduction or complete absence of waste due to product defects. 3D printing generates far less waste than conventional manufacturing methods, and it has the potential to help separate the creation of social and economic benefits from the negative impact of industry on the environment in the minds of consumers. In addition to reducing waste, 3D printing saves energy. The Federation of Metal Powder Industries conducted a study comparing subtractive manufacturing of a truck gear with additive manufacturing of the same part. In the first case, the product needs to go through 17 stages of production, while in the second - only six. 3D printing uses half the energy of traditional technologies.

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ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ IGCT ТИРИСТОРА

Abstract:

В статье исследуется возможность применения IGCT тиристора (с интегрированным затвором) в силовых выпрямительных системах большой мощности. Предлагается оптимальная топология преобразователя мощности, полностью использующая функциональные возможности IGCT. Предлагаемое решение генерирует относительно плавный выходной постоянный ток с меньшим содержанием высокочастотных гармоник, что позволяет избежать проблем, связанных с высокочастотными гармониками, которые встречаются в силовых выпрямителях на основе IGBT. IGCT будет играть значительную роль в повышении рентабельности и надежности в системах выпрямителей больших токов и большой мощности низкого и среднего диапазона.

Key words:

Инвертор, МСТ Запираемые тиристоры с полевым управлением, минимальная длительность импульса, напряжения отсечки, запираемые тиристоры, IGCT- (Интегрированный тиристор с коммутируемым затвором), MOSFET (металл-окисел-полупроводник), коэффициент полезного действия (КПД).

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Инвертор – это полупроводниковый вентиль, задача которого обратна выпрямителю, то есть преобразование энергии источника постоянного тока в энергию переменного тока. Инверторы подразделяются на два класса: ведомые сетью (зависимые) и автономные. Зависимые инверторы, Ведомые инверторы преобразуют энергию источника постоянного тока в переменный ток с отдачей её в сеть переменного тока, то есть осуществляют преобразование, обратное выпрямителю. Интегрированный тиристор с коммутируемым затвором (IGCT) стал предпочтительным силовым полупроводником в промышленных приложениях среднего напряжения. Также на рынках управления энергопотреблением и тягового усилия универсальность этого переключателя питания позволила повысить производительность и снизить затраты в различных приложениях.[2]

Потери в преобразованиях электрической энергии время включения $t_{вкл}$ и время выключения $t_{выкл}$ полупроводникового вентиля характеризуют соответственно время перехода вентиля из выключенного состояния во включенное и из включенного состояния в выключенное; Благодаря технологии изготовления IGCT тиристоры больше подходит для широкого использования на производственных оборудовании, чем например GTO. GTO имеют время задержки включения порядка 25 мкс, в то время как время задержки включения IGCT уменьшается примерно до 1 мкс из-за его жесткой коммутации затвора. Таким образом, разброс времени задержки IGCT очень мал, что делает возможным их последовательное соединения с небольшими уравнительными затворами.

Однако для последовательного подключения требуются общие демпферы и условия блокировки, т.е. при включении, выключении и в выключенном состоянии (под постоянным напряжением).

Последовательное соединение IGCT всегда требует демпфирование, чтобы разделить напряжение на последовательно соединенных устройствах. Для этого требуется демпфер динамического распределения, выравнивание при переключении. Наиболее распространенными из них являются Демпферы RC- и RCD. Дополнительно статический резистор требуется для разделения (RP). Это нужно для компенсации тока утечки, различия устройств и для нейтрализации разницы напряжений после несбалансированного выключения. Разница во времени между управляющими сигналами в последовательно соединенные IGCT напрямую влияет на распределение напряжения, как показано на рис. трехуровневый преобразователь источника напряжения (VSC) с нейтральной точкой Жазимные диоды (NPC) [4]

Схема моделирования IGCT

Параметры сигнала управления в цепи управляющего электрода тиристора, обеспечивающие его надежное включение: напряжение управления $U_{уэ}$ (несколько вольт), ток управления $I_{уэ}$ (доли ампера), скорость нарастания тока управления $dI_{уэ}/dt$ (1-2 А/мксек), минимальная длительность импульса управления (20...100 мксек). При этом мощность сигнала управления в тысячи раз меньше мощности, переключаемой тиристором в анодной цепи;

Напряжение отсечки спрямленной вольт-амперной характеристики вентиля в прямом направлении U_0 и его динамическое сопротивление $R_{дин}$. На рис. 1. показаны реальная нелинейная и кусочно-линейная модельная (упрощенная) вольт-амперные характеристики вентиля в прямом направлении.

Значение напряжения отсечки для кремниевых вентилях равно около 1В, значение динамического сопротивления обратно пропорционально номинальному среднему значению анодного тока вентиля I_a и меняется в диапазоне от долей ома для маломощных тиристоров до тысячных долей ома для мощных тиристоров, имея порядок $1/I_a$ [Ом]. Эти параметры определяют потери активной мощности в вентиле при прохождении прямого тока, что вызывает разогрев полупроводниковой структуры;- тепловое сопротивление вентиля характеризует его способность отводить тепло от места его выделения, т. е. р-п перехода, и определяется как отношение перепада температуры между двумя средами T на единицу рассеиваемой в вентиле мощности P_v [град/Вт]. Значимы прежде всего три тепловых сопротивления вентиля: р-п переход – корпус вентиля $R_{пк}$, р-п переход – охладитель $R_{по}$, р-п переход – окружающая среда $R_{пс}$.

. Разным способам охлаждения вентиля соответствуют разные тепловые сопротивления, через которые определяется предельная мощность потерь в вентиле (предельное среднее значение анодного тока вентиля), исходя из максимально допустимой температуры р-п перехода (для кремниевых диодов – 150°C, для кремниевых тиристоров – 110...120°C); защитный показатель i_{2dt} есть значение временного интеграла от квадрата ударного прямого тока, появляющегося при аварии, при превышении которого вентиль разрушается. В соответствии с этим показателем, чем больше значение аварийного прямого тока через вентиль, тем меньше должна быть его длительность. Вентили с полным управлением характеризуются тем, что их можно отпереть и запереть при наличии на них прямого напряжения воздействием только по цепи управления.[1]

Основными представителями вентилях с полным управлением являются запираемые (двухоперационные) тиристоры ЗТ (англ. обозначении GTO – Gate Turn Off) и силовые транзисторы (биполярные, полевые и комбинированные, так называемые биполярные транзисторы с изолированным затвором, обозначаемые IGBT – Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor).[2]

Запираемые (двухоперационные) тиристоры отличаются от обычных (однооперационных) тиристоров тем, что их можно запереть подачей короткого, но мощного импульса тока обратной полярности, в цепь управляющего электрода тиристора. Большая величина этого импульса тока определяется тем, что коэффициент усиления по току при запираии тиристора невысок, обычно не более 4-5. Поэтому для запираемого тиристора важно не среднее значение прямого тока, а его максимальное (мгновенное) значение, по которому и маркируются запираемые тиристоры. Достигнутые предельные параметры запираемых тиристоров: по прямому току до 2,5 кА, по напряжению – до 4 кВ, по частоте переключения–до 1кГц, по коэффициенту усиления по току выключения–до 3-5. Условное обозначение GTO тиристора показано на рис. 2, а.

В последние годы GTO-тиристоры были модифицированы и создан новый тип прибора–тиристора, коммутируемый по управляющему электроду (GCT - Gate Commutated Thyristor или IGCT - Integrated Gate Commutated Thyristor).

В них за счет того, что весь ток включения/выключения коммутируется через управляющий электрод, почти на порядок сокращаются время коммутации, а значит, и коммутационные потери. Это позволило сегодня уже создать IGBT на 3кА, 3,5 кВ. При этом для этого тиристора в отличие от GTO-тиристора, не требуется применения снабберов – специальных внешних цепей, формирующих траекторию рабочей точки при выключении тиристора. В простейшем случае это конденсатор, ограничивающий скорость нарастания прямого напряжения на тиристоре при его выключении. Последовательно с конденсатором включается небольшое активное сопротивление для ограничения тока конденсатора. Условное обозначение IGBT-тиристора показано на рис.2, б. [2]

Запираемые тиристоры с полевым управлением (без потребления тока) - MCT (MOS Controlled Thyristor), которые в связи с простотой управления потеснят GTO-тиристоры при условии сопоставимости их предельных электрических параметров.

Рис. 3: Сравнение между GTO 5SGA 40L4501 и GCT 5SGY 35L4502.

Коммутационные потери обоих устройств равны примерно так же.[2]

Принципиальным отличием транзисторов от запираемых и обычных тиристоров, включаемых и выключаемых короткими импульсами управления, является то, что в них необходимо наличие сигнала управления на все время прохождения через транзистор прямого тока. Биполярные транзисторы (BPT) представляют собой трехслойные полупроводниковые структуры p-n-p и n-p-n типов, в которых имеется два p-n перехода: база – эмиттер и база – коллектор.

Биполярный транзистор позволяет за счет изменения тока базы p-n перехода база–эмиттер, смещенного в прямом направлении, управлять в десятки раз большим током, текущим через выходной переход база–коллектор, смещенный в обратном направлении. Так как обратное напряжение на коллекторном (выходном) переходе может быть также в десятки раз больше прямого напряжения на входном переходе база–эмиттер, то получается и большое усиление в транзисторе по напряжению, а значит, очень большое (в сотни и тысячи раз) усиление по мощности.

Условное обозначение и выходные ВАХ биполярного транзистора представлены в строке 1 табл. 1.

Эта возможность транзистора при работе в ключевом (как тиристор) режиме позволяет использовать его в устройствах силовой электроники для управления потоками энергии с целью их преобразования. В закрытом состоянии транзистора ток базы делается равным нулю (точка А на выходных характеристиках), т. е. ключ разомкнут; при этом пренебрегаем малым неуправляемым током коллектора на нижней ВАХ. В открытом состоянии транзистора ток базы устанавливается не меньше такого уровня I_B , чтобы рабочая точка транзистора с заданной внешней цепью величиной тока нагрузки I_n была в положении Б, соответствующем наименьшему возможному напряжению на транзисторе при этом токе, для уменьшения потерь мощности в транзисторе.

Основные недостатки биполярных транзисторов связаны с заметными затратами мощности на управление (управление током по базе) и с недостаточным быстродействием, определяющим скорость перехода рабочей точки транзистора из положения А в положение Б и обратно. Полевые транзисторы в отличие от биполярных транзисторов, работающих с двумя типами носителей тока – электронами и дырками, полевые транзисторы - используют один (униполярный) тип носителей тока. Проводимость канала между истоком и стоком (определенные аналоги эмиттера и коллектора биполярного транзистора) модулируется с помощью электрического поля, прикладываемого к каналу в поперечном направлении с помощью третьего электрода – затвора (управляющего электрода).

Канал может быть двух типов: n-типа или p-типа. Теперь уже управляющим параметром для выходных характеристик является напряжение на затворе (на входе транзистора), а не ток входа, как у биполярных транзисторов. Входная цепь полевого транзистора очень высоким сопротивлением и практически не потребляет ток, т. е. управление полевым транзистором происходит без затраты мощности. У полевого транзистора с каналом p-типа аналогичные свойства и характеристики, только у последних необходимо изменить полярности напряжений на стоке и затворе (относительно истока) на обратную полярность. Эти транзисторы называются MOSFET или FET транзисторами (Metal - Oxide - Semiconductor - Field - Effect Transistor), что соответствует обозначению МОП (МДП) транзистор (металл-окисел - полупроводник), где металл означает электрод затвора, окисел означает диэлектрик, отделяющий затвор от полупроводникового канала между истоком и стоком.[3]

В зависимости от постановки задачи теплового расчета динамические потери могут определяться в каждом транзисторном модуле, или в преобразователе в целом с возможным последующим разделением суммарных потерь на потери в отдельных конструктивных элементах. В последнем случае алгоритм расчета может быть несколько упрощен. В частности, могут быть использованы не отдельные составляющие динамических потерь, изображенные на рис. 22.3, а суммарные динамические потери энергии на одном цикле переключения транзистора (включение транзистора, выключение транзистора, выключение обратного диода). Соответствующая зависимость суммарных потерь за цикл коммутации для модуля типа FZ1600R17KF6CB2 для температуры 125°C представлена на рис. 4.

Рис. 4. Зависимость потерь энергии от тока при полном цикле коммутации модуля типа FZ1600R17KF6CB2 для 125°C

Мощность потерь энергии в силовых полупроводниковых элементах преобразователей составляет обычно от одного до нескольких процентов номинальной мощности преобразователя. Поскольку расчет электромагнитных процессов осуществляется при допущении, что вентили идеальны, то указанные один или несколько процентов можно рассматривать как дополнительную погрешность расчета, которая выражается в дополнительных ошибках в расчете токов и напряжений. Эту погрешность можно практически устранить при введении в схемы преобразователей элементов, параметры которых определяются в результате расчета мощности потерь [1].

Суммарная мощность потерь энергии в вентилях преобразователя равна сумме статических и динамических потерь. Динамические потери энергии в преобразователе в целом определяются как сумма динамических потерь в вентилях фаз.

Выводы.

Полупроводниковые вентили можно использовать для преобразования переменного тока электричества на постоянный ток или наоборот, могут сыграть важную роль в обеспечении глобального устойчивого энергетического решения и защиты окружающей среды. Эффективность преобразования энергии в полупроводниковых вентилях системах намного выше, чем в существующих системах производства электроэнергии. В настоящее время основными проблемами, требующими решения, являются преодоление низкой эффективности и снижение затрат на ватт преобразования энергии. Одним из путей могло бы стать улучшение собственной эффективности используемых в настоящее время полупроводниковых вентилях или поиск новых вентилях преобразователей с хорошими характеристиками, а также низкой стоимостью. Другое решение - оптимизировать эффективность полупроводниковых вентилях устройств. По мере повышения эффективности и снижения затрат ожидается, что диапазон применений полупроводниковых вентилях устройств будет расширяться как в коммерческих, так и в домашних условиях.

Т а б л и ц а 1.

1	<p><u>Биполярные</u> р-р-р п-р-п</p>	
2	<p><u>Полевые (FET)</u> р-п переходом</p> <p>канал n-типа канал p-типа</p>	
3	<p><u>Полевой МДП (MOS) - типа</u> (с изолированным затвором)</p> <p>Со встроенным каналом n-типа p-типа</p>	
	<p>С индуцированным каналом n-типа p-типа</p>	
4	<p><u>Комбинированный (IGBT - транзистор)</u> канал n - типа канал p - типа</p>	

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EXPLORING WAYS TO USE THE THEORY OF MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Abstract:

The article provides a conceptual setting for conscious teaching whereby classroom activities are referred to the principles of MIT. It also advocates an experimental insight into foreign language teaching where both a teacher and a student are encouraged to explore, discover and practice their multiple intelligences while teaching and mastering foreign languages. Additionally, practical implications of MIT for FLT are discussed and illustrated by a few examples of the activities designed in the framework of the theory.

Key words:

foreign language teaching (FLT), theory of Multiple Intelligences (MIT), intelligences, verbal/linguistic intelligence, experimental learning/teaching, learner-centred teaching, individualized instruction, independent learning, success.

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Workspace (Education subject)

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INTRODUCTION

In 1983 Howard Gardner started a revolution in the field of cognitive science introducing the theory of multiple intelligences (MIT) (Gardner, 1983, 1999), and advocating a learner-based philosophy which has become known as "an increasingly popular approach to characterizing the ways in which learners are unique and to developing instruction to respond to this uniqueness" (Richards & Rodgers, 2001). By doing so, Gardner not only challenged the unitary concept of intelligence but also criticized the school systems prevailing so far. Consequently, Gardner's MIT invited educators to exploit the holistic nature of each learner and establish a learner-centred way of teaching with the recognition of each learner's intelligence profile so that teaching became a creative and meaningful enterprise.

THE AIM OF THE STUDY

To establish a new perspective on both effective and creative foreign language teaching (FLT) in the framework of Howard Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences (MIT).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

THE THEORY OF MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES VERSUS TEACHING

The advent of a humanistic approach towards teaching in the 60s of the 20th century brought a new insight into the nature of foreign language teaching replacing conventional methods by non-conventional, student-centered and individualized ways of teaching. The Classical Method as well as the Grammar Translation Method gave way to a number of innovative methods which emphasized the importance of perceiving each student as a "whole person" with their own unique psychological background and physical environment. The recognition of individual learners' affective factors was to make the process of learning efficient.

A range of non-conventional methods such as The Silent way, Total Physical Response, Community Language Learning, Suggestopedia, etc. advocated a learner-based instruction with a low-stress factor and aimed at quick and successful mastery of foreign languages [1,2,3].

What is the success of a foreign language learner determined by? Clearly, it is determined by many factors – both extrinsic and intrinsic – such as motivation, physical conditions, intelligence, learning styles, gender, aptitude and age. Rod Ellis (Ellis, 1985) claims that the success of a foreign language learner relies on the combination of "an academic ability with some cognitive qualities", both of which constitute necessary components of the so-called general intelligence. Therefore, intelligence is closely connected with successful foreign language teaching and learning [4].

The word "intelligence" comes from the Latin verb *intelligere* and means "to understand". Generally, for most of us intelligence seems to have some mystique quality and few people approach IQ tests with enthusiasm feeling that they tend to evaluate intelligence too narrowly limiting it mostly to the ability to think logically and visualize things. What is more, for years intelligence had been perceived as a unitary concept defined operationally as the ability to answer IQ test questions. One of the researchers, who challenged the unitary concept of intelligence was Howard Gardner, a Harvard psychologist researching brain injuries. Criticizing the narrow view on intelligence, he emphasized its pluralistic nature and offered a new insight into the definition of intelligence (Gardner, 1983):

To my mind, a human intellectual competence must entail a set of skills of problem solving – enabling the individual to resolve genuine problems or difficulties that he or she encounters and, when appropriate, to create an effective product – and must also entail the potential for finding or creating problems – thereby laying the groundwork for the acquisition of new knowledge (Emphasis in original)[5].

14

Gardner introduced his theory of multiple intelligences in his book entitled “Frames of Mind” published in 1983. In the book he pointed out that I. Q. tests tend to measure primarily the so-called basic skills – logical/mathematical and spatial abilities – thus offering a limited score of the individuals whose strengths do not lie in these basic skills (Gardner, 1983). Gardner also claimed that school systems of education focus mainly on the basic skills neglecting other skills and talents exhibited by children. He claimed that humans have evolved an ability to carry out several types of intelligences (Gardner, 1983).

1. Verbal/linguistic intelligence	Involves reading, writing and speaking and is respectively exercised through practising reading, writing, speaking and listening skills.
2. Logical-mathematical intelligence	Involves abstract thinking, classifying, sequencing and computing skills and is exercised through mathematics, logic games and puzzles.
3. Musical intelligence	Involves understanding, composing, conducting music and dancing and is exercised through singing, dancing, playing and interpreting music.
4. Spatial intelligence	Involves good visual perception of the environment and the orientation in space and is exercised through practising the graphic and plastic arts, doing spatial tasks and practising imagination.
5. Bodily kinesthetic intelligence	Involves physical coordination, dexterity and a good grasp of motor skills and is exercised through active sports and games.
6. Interpersonal intelligence	Involves the ability to communicate well and understand other people and is exercised through cooperative, group and pair work.
7. Intrapersonal intelligence	Involves understanding one's inner world of emotions, the ability to control them and express them and is exercised through reflection, journal writing and imaginative games.
8. Naturalistic intelligence	Involves understanding Nature as well as the ability to observe, classify and categorize plants and animals and is exercised through exploring and studying Nature.

Gardner firmly believes that the eight intelligences are independent being developed at different times and to different levels in different individuals. He also claims that they are related: each intelligence does influence and enhance the level of other intelligences (Gardner, 1998). Consequently, by practising one's strong intelligences, an individual may enhance the level of his/her weak intelligences, which implies a range of new possibilities for educators[6].

Gardner's introduction of MIT has had an enormous impact on educational systems. Starting from 1983, his ideas have been enthusiastically introduced into the system of education especially in North America. MIT has gained propagators all around the world who continue experimenting with it in the classroom for it is “an increasingly popular approach to characterizing the ways in which learners are unique and to developing instruction to respond to this uniqueness” (Richards, Rogers, 2001).

THE IMPLICATIONS OF MIT FOR SCHOOL SYSTEMS OF EDUCATION

Traditional school systems are designed and many teachers teach as if all learners were the same. Gardner points out that school systems often focus on a narrow range of intelligences emphasizing verbal/linguistic and logical/mathematical skills (Gardner, 1983). This practice results in imposing the reputation of being a weaker and less intelligent pupil if a student does not do well in the basic skills. Consequently, a learner strives through the school years with a hatred for mathematics and language lessons perceiving oneself as a failure. In the light of the prevailing schools' uniformity, MIT brings a positive message focusing on the strongest points of a student so that nobody is seen as a failure. In other words, Gardner offers a new insight into the system of education where the major task of an educator is to encourage children to explore and exercise all types of their intelligences. He also points out the social advantages of his theory put into practice (Gardner, 1993):

It is of the utmost importance that we recognise and nurture all the varied human intelligences, and all of the combinations of the intelligences. We are all so different largely because we all have different combinations of intelligences[7]. If we recognize this, I think we will have at least a better chance of dealing appropriately with the many problems that we face in the world. If we can mobilize the spectrum of human abilities, not only will people feel better about themselves and more competent; it is even possible that they will also feel more engaged and better able to join the rest of the world community in working for the broader good[8].

Thus, creating a rich, stimulating and active environment from the beginning of school education will result in generations of healthier, happier and brighter people (Gardner, 1999):

I want my children to understand the world, but not just because the world is fascinating and the human mind is curious. I want them to understand it so that they will be positioned to make it a better place [9]. Knowledge is not the same as morality, but we need to understand if we are to avoid past mistakes and move in productive directions. An important part of that understanding is knowing who we are and what we can do... Ultimately, we must synthesize our understandings for ourselves. The performance of understanding that try matters are the ones we carry out as human beings in an imperfect world which we can affect for good or for ill [10].

Obviously, the advantages of the MIT as used in the classroom are many for it helps teachers to create a more personalized and diversified syllabus where instruction is matched to learning styles (Gardner, 1993):

"Seven kinds of intelligence would allow seven ways to teach, rather than one. And powerful constraints that exist in the mind can be mobilized to introduce a particular concept (or whole system of thinking) in a way that children are most likely to learn it and least likely to distort it. Paradoxically, constraints can be suggestive and ultimately freeing."

Another advantage of MIT is that by focusing on success rather than failure it helps to create a positive atmosphere thus enhancing both extrinsic and intrinsic motivation of learners. What is more, teachers are encouraged to broaden their workshop by assisting in helping students become empowered learners (Kornhaber, 2001):

"[...] the theory validates educators' everyday experience: students think and learn in many different ways. It also provides educators with a conceptual framework for organizing and reflecting on curriculum assessment and pedagogical practices [11]. In turn, this reflection has led many educators to develop new approaches that might better meet the needs of the range of learners in their classrooms."

Finally, with the use of MIT concepts classes gain a spirit of adventure and discovery where both teachers and students are encouraged to experiment. Certainly, teaching concepts, when related to MIT, tend to produce self-efficient and motivated learners, who perceive the process of their education as being creative and dynamic. What is more, the teachers incorporating their teaching syllabus into the MIT concepts will enjoy a never ending challenge of creative and experimental teaching [12].

THE THEORY OF MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

In recent years there has been great research done in the field of foreign language teaching methodology. Much emphasis has been given to the research of different learning styles and learners' profiles [13]. Reid mentions some of the major directions in this research: multiple intelligences, perceptual learning styles, field dependence/independence, analytic/global learning styles and reflective/impulsive learning styles (Ride, 1999). Learners' greater awareness of their own styles of learning has resulted in a more effective foreign language teaching making them realise their own responsibility for the outcome: "higher interest and motivation in the learning process, increased student responsibility for their own learning, and greater classroom community. These are affective changes, and the changes have resulted in more effective learning" (Ride, 1999).

Although Gardner does not make a direct reference to foreign language teaching, MIT has been successfully used in FLT. This experience has brought successful results with students of different nationalities, ages and abilities, and has been accepted with much enthusiasm by their teachers and parents. When used in a foreign language classroom, it allows each student to draw from their own strengths to approach learning and creates an opportunity to learn a foreign language in a meaningful context wherein verbal intelligence is practised in combination with other intelligences [14].

According to MIT, a good language learner is a learner who has a well-developed verbal/linguistic intelligence which implies that some learners are better-equipped for learning a foreign language. On the other hand, those who cannot boast about their verbal intelligence can still enjoy and succeed in language learning because it can be supported by using their musical, bodily-kinaesthetic, interpersonal, intrapersonal, mathematical and naturalistic abilities since "they constitute frames for working on the same linguistic content" (Arnold & Fonseca, 2004).

Certainly, many foreign language teachers find MIT a perfectly acceptable addition to every school curriculum and an invaluable tool for the transformation of education: "From a teaching point of view, it is [...] important to recognise the fact that learners are in fact different and therefore learn differently [15]. Only in doing so can teachers fully encourage their learners to try harder and at the same time make the learning environment as meaningful and enjoyable as possible for the parties involved" (Palmberg, 2002).

Hopefully, more and more foreign language teachers will want to face the challenge of using MIT during their lessons for it is absolutely worth the effort and time spent on the preparation of the activities based on MI.

RESULTS

FLT ACTIVITIES DESIGNED IN THE FRAMEWORK OF MIT

Below are given sample exercises designed in the framework of MIT to be used during foreign language lessons with students of different age and level. They aim at practising language skills through the use of different types of intelligences. Therefore, they cater for different types of learners' intelligence profiles allowing each student to base their foreign language practice on the profile they are good at and therefore, improve their motivational drive.

"My journal"

The activity aims at developing verbal-linguistic and intrapersonal intelligences. The focus is on developing the ability to identify and express one's thoughts and emotions. The activity can be used even with post-beginners. It aims at developing free-writing [16].

Procedure:

Students are asked to keep a diary where they are to comment on their everyday experiences in the classroom. From time to time a teacher collects diaries and comments on what each student has written in the diary.

"The place I live in"

The activity aims at developing visual-spatial and interpersonal intelligences. Being a hands-on activity, it also promotes a cooperative learning. The focus is on the description of the place the students live in with the emphasis on urban vocabulary [17].

Procedure:

Students are asked to bring cardboard, boxes, brightly-coloured paper, glue, etc. They work in groups. Using the materials they have brought, they have to make a building/buildings they have visited/seen in their town/city.

When they finish, students get together to build a single model of their city/town placing the buildings they have built in the correct street. When the model of the city/town is ready, students name the streets. Finally, they describe the town/city in English [18].

"Who are you in the mirror?"

The activity aims at developing intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligences.

The goal is to help students to identify feelings and express emotions adequately.

Procedure:

Students are asked to bring mirrors into the classroom. The teacher uses flashcards to show people's faces expressing different emotions. Students have to identify the feeling or emotions and then imitate these emotions in the mirrors [19].

CONCLUSIONS

MIT becomes a perfect ingredient to a foreign language curriculum for it caters for learners' individual differences and advocates an individual approach towards FLT enabling both the teacher and learner to master a foreign language in an efficient, meaningful and creative way. Therefore, foreign language teachers should experiment with MIT for a number of reasons: firstly, to establish a student-oriented insight into teaching; secondly, to provide a meaningful context for teaching; and finally, to increase the level of their students' motivation to learn a foreign language.

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TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING AHAMIYATI

Abstract:

Maqola bugungi kundagi Respublikamiz oldida turgan dolzarb masalalarni yechimini topishga qaratilgan "raqamli tadbirkorlikni" rivojlantirish bo'yicha konseptual yondashuvlarni, hamda xorij tajribasini o'rganish va uni Respublikamizga mos jihatlaridan foydalanishning yangi yo'nalishlarini taklif etish, shuningdek O'zbekiston Respublikasida "raqamli tadbirkorlikni" rivojlantirish uchun taklif va tavsiyalar berishga bag'ishlangan.

Key words:

raqamli iqtisodiyot, raqamli tadbirkorlik, innovatsiya, virtual muhit, raqamli texnologiyalar

Author of the article:

Turdaliyeva Og'iloy

Workspace (Education subject)

Andijan qishloq xo'jaligi va agrotexnologiyalar insituti talabalasi

KIRISH

Raqamli iqtisodiyot - bu siyosiy- iqtisodiy, ilmiy-ijtimoiy, madaniy va ma'rifiy munosabatlardagialoqalarni raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llash yordamidaamalga oshiruvchi yangi tizim bo'lib, raqamli iqtisodiyotsharoitida "raqamli tadbirkorlik" alohida ahamiyatgaegadir.

ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

Ta'kidlash zarurki, jahonda ko'zga ko'ringan xorijlikiqtisodchi olimlardan - A. Bxayd, Dj.K. Gelbreyt, U. Zalman, I.M. Kirsner, L. fon Mizes, F. Nayt, Dj. Stensill, F. Xayek, Y. Shumpeter ,K.V. Aysel, M.P. Voynarenko, G.K. Ginsa, P.Yu. Yerofo- yeva, M.Z. Ilchikova, G.B. Kleyner, Ye.Ye. Kuzmina, L.P. Kuzmina, G.S. Merzlikina, A.F. Moskovseva, Ye.F. Cheberko L.S. Shaxovskaya va boshqalar, O'zbekistondaA.Abduganiev, Q.Abduraxmonov, X.Abulqosimov, Z.Xudoyberdiev, Z.Tolametova kabi olimlartadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish masalalarini katta e'tibor bilan o'rganganlar. Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitidaraqamli tadbirkorlik masalalari V.Yu. Pestov, B.G. Preobrajenskiy, N.A. Serebryakova, T.O. Tolstix kabiolimlarning ilmiy izlanishlarida o'z ifodasini topgan.

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI VA EMPIRIK TAHLIL

Raqamli iqtisodiyotni asosiy vazifalari:

- raqamli biznes va tadbirkorlikni yaratish;
- korxonalarni barqaror rivojlantirishga yordamberuvchi investitsiyalar bilan ta'minlashga alohidae'tibor qaratish;
- innovatsion faoliyatni amalga oshiruvchi malakalikadrlar bilan ta'minlash.

Raqamli iqtisodiyot kichik biznes va xususiytadbirkorlikni rivojlanishida alohida ahamiyatga egadir.

Shu o'rinda ta'kidlab o'tishimiz zarurki, kichikbiznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni asosiy xususiyatlariquyidagilardan iboratdir;

texnologik va boshqaruvni egiluvchanliginita'minlay olish.

Hozirgi raqamli iqtisodiyot asrida biznesni yuritishqoidalari ham o'zgarib borayotganligini kuzatishmumkin. An'anaviy iqtisodiyot sharoitida xaridorlarishlab chiqaruvchi tomonidan qanday tovar yokixizmatlar taklif etilsa shunga qanoat qilgan bo'lsa, raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida esa iste'molchi bozorga o'zxohishini, takliflarini bayon etadi. Raqamli transformatsiyalar biznesmenga zamonaviy bozorgabog'lanish uchun o'z biznesini yaxshilashga majburetadi. Raqamli iqtisodiyotda xarajatlarni qisqarishinatijasida ko'rsatilayotgan xizmatlarning qiymatlarzonlashib boradi, daro- mad topishning yangiyo'nalishlarini keltirib chiqaradi.

Bundan tashqari, raqamli tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishnatijasida, tovar va xizmat- lar global bozorlarga tezdataklif etiladi, mazkur tovar va xizmatlar xususida esadunyo- ning istalgan hududiga ma'lumotlar taqdimetiladi. Raqamli tadbirkorlik yangi biznes modellarniishlab chiqilishini, yangi bozorlarga kirib borishimkoniyatlarini yaratadi.

Raqamli tadbirkorlar ishlab chiqarishga yangitexnologiyalarni kiritadilar va avtomatlashtirishjarayonini amalga oshiradilar. Raqamlashtirish vagloballashuv bir birlari bilan uzviy bog'liqdir.

Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida tadbirkor ishlabchiqarishni yangidan yangi kombinatsiyalarni yaratadi, o'z faoliyatiga turli xildagi yangi texnologiyalarni tatbiqetadi. Hozirgi vaqtda dunyo miqyosida tadbirkorlikniyangi ko'rinishlari, ya'ni raqamli tadbirkorlik, innovatsion tadbirkorlik,venchur tadbirkorligi kabilarrivojlanmoqda.

Raqamli iqtisodiyotni shakllantirish sharoitida ishlabchiqarish jarayoniga innovatsiyalarni, zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarni joriy etish iqtisodiyotning yangi bilimayo'naltirilgan tarmoqlarini paydo bo'lishiga olibkelmoqda. Iqtisodiyotning innovatsion sektorini, shuningdek "raqamli tadbirkorlikni" shakllanishi varivojlanishi ishlab chiqaruvchilarni raqobatbardoshligini oshirish imkoniyatini yaratadi.

Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida "raqamli tadbirkorlik" aloxida axamiyatga ega bo'lib, unda tadbirkorlik faoliyatida mukammal innovatsion qarorlarni qabul qilish muhimdir.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida raqamli iqtisodiyotni shakllantirish jarayonida "raqamli tadbirkorlikni" rivojlantirish innovatsion jarayonlari bilan bevositabog'liqdir. Innovatsiya – yangilik kiritish ularni turlisoha, tarmoqlarda qo'llashdir.

Mamlakatni jadal innovatsion rivojlantirish uchun ishlab chiqarishni modernizatsiya qilish, texnik va texnologik jihatdan yangilash jarayonlariga ilmiy-amaliy tadqiqotlar natijalarini va nou-xau ishlanmalarni keng joriy etish, shuningdek ilmiy muassasalar va real iqtisodiyot tarmoqlari korxonalarini o'rtasida hamkorlikni o'rnatish zarurdir.

XULOSA VA MUNOZARA

O'zbekiston Respublikasi iqtisodiyotini tarmoqlarini, jumladan tadbirkorlik faoliyatini innovatsion usulda rivojlantirish O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh. Mirziyoyev tomonidan qo'yilgan eng dolzarb vazifalardan biridir. Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirish mamlakatimiz fuqarolarining turmush farovonligini oshirish, kambag'allikni kamaytirish, iqtisodiy taraqqiyotga erishishning muhim shartidir.

Bugungi kunda dunyodagi rivojlangan mamlakatlarda aholi daromadlarining o'sishi birinchi navbatda tadbirkorlikda innovatsion jarayonlarning to'g'ri tashkil etilishi hamda "raqamli tadbirkorlikni" doimiy ravishda takomillashtirib borilayotgani bilan bog'liqdir.

Raqamli iqtisodiyotni shakllantirish sharoitida Respublikamiz oldida turgan muhim vazifalardan birinchi bo'lib raqobatbardosh bo'lgan mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish va xizmatlar ko'rsatishni keng yo'lga qo'yishdir.

Bugungi kundagi asosiy vazifalardan birinchi bo'lib o'rtasida sog'lom raqobatni ta'minlash orqali, narxlarni pasaytirish va jahon bozorida raqobatbardosh, eksport bop sifatli mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarishni kengaytirishdir. Xalqaro tajribani o'rgangan holda monopoliya sohalariga xususiy sektor uchun yanada keng yo'l ochish, "raqamli tadbirkorlikni" rivojlantirish va shu orqali raqobat muhitini shakllantirish lozim.

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IMPROVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN CONSTRUCTION

Abstract:

Ways and details of increasing energy efficiency and rational use of the buildings under construction are highlighted, and the work being done in this regard, in the world and in Uzbekistan, is presented.

Key words:

Energy efficient house, energy sources, building, thermal insulation, energy consumption, energy audit.

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Workspace (Education subject)

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One of the modern trends in housing construction is to carry out design and construction works taking into account the convenience, environmental and energy efficiency of the houses that are planned to be built.

As we know, the main sources of energy in the world are reserves (oil, gas and coal). According to experts' calculations, energy sources can last up to 100 years. In many developed countries, almost half of the energy consumption falls on houses. Therefore, one of the main ways to save resources is to improve the energy efficiency of buildings.

The main principle of designing an energy-efficient house is to maintain a comfortable internal temperature without the use of ventilation and heating systems by using alternative energy sources.

The criteria for classifying such houses is energy consumption: if annual heating costs are less than 90 kWh/m², the house is energy efficient; If it is less than 45 kWh/m², it saves less energy; Less than 15 kWh / m² energy consumption is considered zero (nothing is spent on heating, but energy is required to prepare hot water).

The first experimental energy-efficient building appeared in Manchester (USA) in 1974 after the global energy crisis.

Targeted state programs have been developed in Denmark, Germany and Finland for such energy saving and construction of energy-efficient buildings.

10 kilometers outside Helsinki, the capital of Finland, is Vikki, a neighborhood of energy-efficient buildings (local population 5,500 and land area 1,132 hectares). It accounts for 50 percent of the neighborhood's solar energy use and hot water needs.

The total area of solar collectors is 1248 m². Energy-saving technology and alternative energy consumption can reduce energy consumption by 40% compared to conventional houses.

Denmark is currently the city of Egedal. According to the state program, the construction of all energy-efficient residential buildings was carried out in South Stenlos. These local citizens do not limit their buildings to ecology and energy saving, but also provide ready-made houses equipped with all energy-saving innovations.

The following constructive and engineering planning solutions are used to minimize energy consumption.

From the point of view of planning, to reduce the area of the walls of 1-3-story houses and their facades (glazing) and thereby prevent heat loss.

Therefore, the main thing is to design a drum at the entrance and build the house facing south, because the main source of heat for heating the house is solar energy.

The houses are prevented from being shaded by other buildings and trees. The heat transfer resistance of the walls should not exceed 0.15 kW/m², for this, internal or double (internal and external) thermal insulation is used.

Today, in our Republic, the development of the way of living of the population in rural areas, the construction of houses on the basis of model projects is inextricably linked with the development of rural infrastructures and the construction of infrastructure facilities. Many houses and apartments on the basis of model projects in accordance with the "Program for the construction of affordable housing on updated model projects in rural areas in 2017-2021" approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2639 dated October 21, 2016 was built and a family in need of improvement of living conditions was provided with housing.

Also, in our country, today attention is paid to the issue of building energy-efficient, economical houses as one of the most important factors in the development of the construction industry, in particular, residential buildings and social sector buildings, which are built on the basis of model projects in rural and urban areas within the framework of state programs. Enrichment with these features is defined as the main task.

Adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on November 14, 2018

According to the Decree No. PF-5577 "On additional measures to improve the state regulation of the construction industry", starting from January 1, 2020, housing construction objects are at the stage of design-research and construction-assembly work. mandatory equipment with energy-efficient and energy-saving equipment is strictly defined.

800 low-carbon three-room energy-efficient houses were built in Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Fergana, Khorezm and Bukhara regions within the framework of the project "Supporting the development of energy-efficient rural housing construction in Uzbekistan". Photoelectric plants (FES) with a capacity of 300 Watts are installed and working in each of these houses for lighting needs. Ten such houses are equipped with solar water heaters capable of heating 200 liters of water. However, such a level of energy consumption in the building remains for 3 to 5 years, and then begins to increase again. It is necessary to carry out an energy audit to determine the reasons for this decrease in energy efficiency. Therefore, it is recommended to conduct an energy audit once every four years. It is worth mentioning that 800 energy-efficient houses built in 2019 within the framework of our project "Supporting the development of energy-efficient rural housing construction in Uzbekistan" in cooperation with the Global Ecology Fund and the Ministry of Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan have installed 300-watt photoelectric stations (FES) are installed. An energy audit will be conducted in 60 houses selected from among these constructed buildings and ordinary model houses built in 2018 within the framework of the State program. This approach makes it possible to compare energy-efficient houses with ordinary houses and to analyze the effectiveness of using energy-efficient and low-carbon technologies in reducing heat and electricity consumption in rural houses.

The widespread introduction of energy audit, the use of renewable energy sources is one of the important and not yet fully exploited reserves. It will help solve the problem of natural gas and oil shortages in the future and, according to experts, it can double the energy costs of consumers.

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BIRINCHI SINIF O'QUVCHILARIGA GEOMETRIK SHAKLLARNI O'RGATISH USULLARI

Abstract:

Bu maqola orqali boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining matematika darslaridagi geometrik tushunchalar va ularni bolalarga o'rgatish usullari haqida takliflar berilgan. Bolalarning geometrik tushunchalar haqidagi tasavvurlarini rivojlantirish haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Key words:

Geometrik shakllar: burchaklar, uchburchak, to'rtburchak, aylana, doira, kvadrat

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Yer yuzidagi barcha mamlakatlar o'z davlatini har bir sohada birinchi o'rinda bo'lishini, yuksak taraqqiy etishini, rivojlanishini xohlaydi buning uchun, albatta, harakat qilish va barcha amallarni bajarish kerak. Bu borada bizning davlatimiz ham jahondagi ko'plab mamlakatlardan qolishmagan holda tashabbuskor harakatlar olib bormoqda. Bunga yaqqol dalil sifatida muhtaram prezidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoyevning so'nggi yillarda olib borilayotgan islohotlarini, chiqarayotgan qonunlarini olishimiz mumkin. Ayniqsa, bugungi kunda O'zbekistonni rivojlantirishda ta'lim sohasidagi o'zgarishlar muhim ro'l o'ynaydi, chunki jahondagi yetakchi mamlakatlarni muvaffaqiyatining bosqichi o'rganilganda uning asosini ta'lim sifati, ta'limdagi o'zgarishlar tashkil etishi aniqlangan. Shu o'rinda muhtaram prezidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoyevning "Hammamiz aziz farzandlarimiz hayoti va taqdirini o'qituvchi va murabbiylarga ishonib topshiramiz. Mana shunday beqiyos boylik posponlari, kelajak bunyodkorlari bo'lgan bu mo'tabar zotlarga munosib hurmat-ehtiram ko'rsatishimiz kerak"--degan fikrlarini yodga olishimiz o'rinli bo'ladi. Shubhasiz, ta'limdagi o'zgarish islohot maktabdan boshlanadi. Maktabning poydevorini, albatta, boshlang'ich ta'lim tashkil etadi. Bu yerdagi mas'uliyat boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilariga borib taqaladi. Boshlang'ich ta'limda o'quvchilarning har bir fanni mukammal o'zlashtirishlari fan o'qituvchilarining fanlarni bor imkoniyatlari bilan samarali tizimni yo'lga qo'ygan holda olib borishlariga bog'liqdir. Har bir fanni o'z ahamiyati o'quvchilar uchun foydali taraflari bisyor. Hech bir fanni matematikasiz tasavvur qilib bo'lmaydi. Matematika deganimizda boshlang'ich sinflardada ko'z oldimizga arifmetik amallar va geometrik shakllar keladi. 1-sinf matematika darsligini ko'rib chiqamiz. Quyidagicha boblar berilgan:

1-bob. Narsalarning to'plamlari
2-bob. 1 dan 10 gacha bo'lgan sonlar
3-bob. 10 ichida qo'shish va ayirish
4-bob. Geometrik shakllar
5-bob. 11 dan 20 gacha bo'lgan sonlar
6-bob. 20 ichida sonlarni o'nlikdan o'tib qo'shish va ayirish
7-bob. 20 ichida qo'shish va ayirish
8-bob. 21 dan 100 gacha bo'lgan sonlar
9-bob. 100 ichida qo'shish va ayirish
10-bob. Ma'lumotlar bilan ishlash
Shu boblardan biz 4-bob bilan chuqurroq tanishib chiqamiz. Birinchi burchaklar bilan tanishamiz. Burchaklar 3 ga bo'linadi: to'g'ri burchak, o'tkir burchak, o'tmas burchak. Endi to'g'ri burchak nimaligini tasavvur qilib bilib olamiz. Doskamizning har bir burchagi to'g'ri burchak shaklida yoki partamizning har bir burchagi to'g'ri burchak shaklida. O'tkir burchak. To'g'ri burchakdan kichik bo'lgan burchakdir. O'tmas burchak esa to'g'ri burchakdan katta bo'lgan burchakdir. Geometrik shakllarga kirishni boshlaymiz endi. Uchburchak va uning elementlari bilan tanishamiz. Avvalo, uchburchak shaklini tasavvur qilib olamiz. Hammamiz ko'z oldimizga uyimizning tomini keltiramiz. Uyimiz tomi uchburchak shaklidir. Uchburchakning 3 ta uchi, 3 ta tomoni, 3 ta burchagi bor. Endi keyingi shakl bilan tanishamiz. To'rtburchak buni ko'z oldimizga keltirish uchun televizorni tasavvur qilamiz televizor to'rt burchak shaklida. To'rtburchakda 4 ta burchak, 4 ta tomon, 4 ta uch bor. O'quvchilarga biz har bir shaklnig maketini ko'rsatib tushuntirish orqali bolalardagi tasavvurni yetarli darajada shakllantira olamiz. Dars jarayonida geometrik shakllarning: to'rtburchak, uchburchak, kvadrat, aylana, doira shaklini albatta jonli tarzda bolga ko'rsatishimiz kerak.

Misol uchun to'rtburchak shaklini daftarimizning shakli orqali ko'rsatib tushuntira olamiz. Bundan tashqari bu shakllarning maketini dars jarayonida yasash orqali mukammal natijaga erisha olamiz. Bolalar har bir shaklni o'z qollari bilan yasab uning nomini aytish orqali bu shakllarni va ular orasidagi farqni tez va oson o'rganib olishadi. Bundan tashqari biz aylana va doirani quyidagicha izohlashimiz mumkin. Aylanani tasavvur qilish uchun velosipedning g'ildiragini eslaymiz. Velosipedning g'ildiragi aylana shaklida. Doiraga esa soatni, nonni misol qilishimiz mumkin.

Xulosa qilib aytganda biz bolalarga matematikani o'rgatishda umuman olganda ta'lim berishda, avvalo, o'zimiz shu mavzu yuzasidan chuqur bilimlarga ega bo'lishimiz va uni bolalarga turli xil usul, metodlar bilan tushuntirib berishimiz zarurdir. Biz berayotgan bilimlar bolalarda samarali natijalar berishi bizning bosh maqsadimiz bo'lishi kerak.

Bolalarda geometrik shakllar haqidagi tushunchalarni shakllantirish juda muhim. Chunki, bu orqali biz o'quvchining fikr yuritish jarayoniga faol ta'sir ko'rsatamiz va bu boladagi tasavvur olamini yetarli darajada kengaytirishning asosiy yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'la oladi.

Adabiyotlar.

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The author is personally responsible for the articles published in the journal. The magazine is published online and in print versions twice in 1 month.

